

The Competence-Based Development of Village Government Personnel towards Superior and Independent Villages in Banyumas Regency, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: The shift in government paradigm has also affected the village government system in Indonesia. Previously, villages were the subordinate of the regency government. Nowadays, they have been autonomous governments. This, in a sense, is an advancement, yet it also poses challenges regarding how the autonomy shall be implemented, particularly the low competence that village government personnel have. Therefore, it needs to develop using a competency-based model. This research aims at identifying the competencies needed by village government personnel's offices and preparing their competence standards. The method employed is survey and the data are collected using questionnaires, interviews, focussed group discussions, and documentation. The data are analyzed using descriptive statistics. The research is conducted in Banyumas Regency. The research results indicate that 3 (three) competencies are identified, namely managerial, sociocultural and technical competencies. The last one includes general and specific technical competencies. Each of these competencies is deemed as either "highly necessary" or "necessary" one by village government personnel. This shows that the said competencies are the ones needed by these village personnel's offices. The identified competencies are used as the basis for preparing competence dictionaries and competence standards for village government personnel's offices.

KEYWORDS: Managerial Competence, Personnel Development, Sociocultural Competence, Technical Competence

A. INTRODUCTION

The shift in government governance paradigm from centralization towards decentralization in Indonesia sets villages free from its state subordination position to an autonomous political entity and legal society unity with an authority to govern and manage their own life. Villages are authorized to prepare and decide on the regulations needed to manage their resources based on their potentials and people's aspiration, and implement and, finally, evaluate them.

This village autonomy gains its legal force from the implementation of Law Number 6 Year 2014 concerning Village. Two (2) strategies are stated to strengthen villages in the law, namely political and economic ones. Politically, there is a transfer of administrative authority from the (central) government to village government, allowing the village government to own the authority to organize and operate the village administration in the effort of developing the village and empowering the villagers towards the dream of a prosperous village society. Economically, it authorizes village governments to manage their finance, from such aspects as income, expenditure, and spending. Currently, villages have gained the expected great force, i.e. becoming an autonomous institution with an authority to manage and handle their own affairs based on the village's own local aspirations and potentials. This great force is an opportunity and challenge at the same time for villages in realizing village development and community empowerment to make them stronger, developed, independent, democratic, and prosperous. Furthermore, as they are authorized to manage 10% (ten percent) of the total State Budget (APBN), or approximately 1.4 billion allocated for each village, the opportunity to be independent and prosperous villages should be greater.

On the other hand, the quality of village government personnel is still limited, thus it is of concern that they might not perform well. Most village government personnel in Indonesia are graduates of Junior High Schools (SMP). This concern can actually be solved and anticipated by building the village government personnel resources. They are the key leverage to the successful village development and community empowerment which constitute the mission of the Village Law itself. Despite their relatively low formal education, the competence of village government personnel can actually still be developed in order to fulfill the competence

demanded for their offices. This research is conducted in order to develop these competence, thus the development of village government personnel resources in this research is competence-based, i.e. an attempt to improve the human resources quality through competences in such a way that human resources with appropriate capabilities as needed and required by their jobs/offices can be manifested (Armstrong, 2006; Martin, 2002; Spencer and Spencer, 1993). One strength of competence-based development model is its ability in creating human resources with competitive advantages (Mitrani et al, 1992; Spencer and Spencer, 1993).

This research is conducted in Banyumas Regency since the village government personnel resources in this regency have relatively low quality. The said village government personnel are spread in 301 villages, making a total of 3,541 personnel consisting of 301 village chiefs, 301 village secretaries, and 2,939 other village personnel. Out of these numbers, 193 (64.1%) village chiefs, 145 (48.2%) village secretaries and 1,850 (62.9%) other village government personnel are graduates of senior high schools or equal (Bagian Pemerintahan Setda Kabupaten Banyumas, 2017).

Based on this problem, the question in this research is “what competences are needed by the village government personnel’s offices to realize the superior and independent village in Banyumas Regency ?” The aim is to prepare an office competence standard for village government personnel offices towards superior and independent villages.

B. RESEARCH METHOD

This is a survey research, meaning that it takes its sample from a population using questionnaire as the main tool for collecting data. The survey is intended to describe the competences needed by village government personnel to enable them to successfully perform their office duties. The research population is village government personnel in Banyumas Regency, amounting to 3.541 personnel consisting of 301 village chiefs, 301 village secretaries, and 2.939 other village personnel. The sample is taken using stratified cluster sampling. The population is homogenous, thus 81 respondents are taken as the sample. The research variable is office competence and it is measured using three indicators, namely managerial, sociocultural and technical competences. The data are collected using questionnaire, observation, focus group discussion, documentation, and interview. The data are analyzed using descriptive statistic.

C. THEORETICAL/CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Competence can be defined as knowledge, skill, attitude, experience, train or characters which may lead individuals to their success in performing their job duties. Competence predicts one’s success in their works. It also improves trust in their relation with clients (Ramlall, 2006). There are six important competences, namely leadership skill, problem-solving skill, communication skill, customer orientation, output orientation and team orientation. Competence will allow human resources to have competitive advantages. Competence allows an individual to qualify for playing a specific role (Abraham et al, 2001; Hoffmann, 1999). The strategic contribution of competence is that it improves the financial competitiveness and adds the value of human resources function. The relationship between competence and organizational performance is focused on the relationship between business activities and employees, business activities, strategic plan and customer value. Competence model also has the potential of improving organizational performance and employee satisfaction (Boselie, 2005; Eichinger & Ulrich, 1995; Mansfield, 1996).

Several studies found that the successfully competing organizations were those which were capable of aligning their competence standards and their organizational plans. Some organizations even require innovative competence in the face of changes. Therefore, a competence framework is used as a model in the center for administrative education and joint practice in an organization (Garavan dan McGuire, 2001). The human resources system suggests that a sustainable competitive advantage should be facilitated with competence growth. Furthermore, it is important that a list of competences be reviewed continuously to match the need for competence in the future (Chen, 2005).

D. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Astronomically, Banyumas Regency is a low land with its average height being ± 108 meters above mean sea level, located in the southern sphere of equator line between $7^{\circ} 15' 05''$ and $7^{\circ} 37' 10''$ South Latitude and between $108^{\circ} 39' 17''$ and $109^{\circ} 27' 15''$ East Longitude. Banyumas Regency’s area in 2017 was 1.327.59 km² or equal to 132.759.56 ha, with its geographical state between lands and mountains consisting of partially Serayu River valley for farming lands. Some plateaus are used for residence and yards, and some mountainous areas are used for plantations, and the tropical forest area is located South to Mount Slamet slope. Based on

its elevation (height above mean sea level), the 54.86% of land in Banyumas Regency is located at 0-100 meters and 45.14% is at 101-500 meters. Banyumas Regency has 27 districts with 331 villages and is led by a Regent and Vice Regent. Each district is led by a *Camat* or District Chief, and 30 *kelurahan* (urban communities equal to villages) are led by *Lurah* and 301 villages are led by Village Chiefs.

Importance of Village Government Personnel Competences

Village government personnel in Banyumas Regency view competences, be it managerial, sociocultural and technical, as something of high importance in performing their office duties. This can be seen from the research result as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Description of Competence Category of Village Government Personnel Offices

No.	Competence Aspect	Category				
		Highly Necessary	Necessary	Fairly Necessary	Unnecessary	Highly Unnecessary
1.	Managerial	75.9%	24.1%	-	-	-
2.	Sociocultural	57.4%	42.6%	-	-	-
3.	Technical	18.5%	81.5%	-	-	-

Source: Processed primary data, 2018

The table above shows that 75.9% of village government personnel thought managerial competence as “highly necessary” and 24.1% thought it was “necessary” in performing their office duties. Managerial competence is the ability to manage, organize, coordinate and mobilize resources in order to achieve the organization’s goals. Next, 57.4% of village government personnel thought sociocultural competence as “highly necessary” and 42.6% thought it was “necessary” in performing their office duties. Sociocultural competence is the ability to interact with diverse community in terms of their religions, races and cultures, behaviors, nationalism insight, ethics, values, morals, emotions and principles which should be fulfilled by village personnel in performing their office duties. Finally, 18.5% of village government personnel thought technical competence as “highly necessary” and 81.5% thought it was “necessary” for village government personnel to have technical competence in supporting their management of village administration. Technical competence is a specific ability related to their office technical fields.

It is highly necessary for village government personnel to have competences in performing the village administration system, particularly in terms of village financial management. Village personnel should own competences given the fact that they are planner, implementor and evaluator of all programs implemented in the villages. The village personnel competences will improve the information in financial statements (Anto and Amir, 2017; Simon et al, 2016). This research result is consistent with the statement above.

Managerial Competence

Particularly for managerial competence, most village personnel, or on average 75.9%, thought this competence was “highly necessary” in performing their office duties. The higher the office rank, the more necessary and even 100% absolutely necessary for the office holders to have it, i.e. village chief and secretary.

Table 2. Cross-Tabulation of Managerial Competence and Village Personnel Office

No.	Office	Managerial Competence Category				
		Highly Necessary	Necessary	Fairly Necessary	Unnecessary	Highly Unnecessary
1.	Village Chief	100%	-	-	-	-
2.	Village Secretaries	100%	-	-	-	-
3.	Administrative Division Chief	66.7%	33.3%	-	-	-
4.	Financial Division Chief	66.7%	33.3%	-	-	-
5.	Planning Division Chief	66.7%	33.3%	-	-	-

6.	Governmental Section Chief	100%	-	-	-	-
7.	Welfare Section Chief	50%	50%	-	-	-
8.	Service Section Chief	83.3%	16.7%	-	-	-
9.	Hamlet Chief	50%	50%	-	-	-
MEAN		75.9%	24.1%	-	-	-

The research result is consistent with previous studies, i.e. identifying and developing managerial competence are important means in managing human resources in order to the organization’s strategic goals. Competence helps the human resources system to focus on the development of employee’s attitude and work quality which support the missions, values, and strategic goals (Rothwell, 2004; Sanghi, 2007; Hijazeh, 2011; Qadeer & Hussain, 2016).

The research result shows that the higher the office of village personnel, the more they need for the managerial competence. This means, at each management level, different managerial competences are needed. The same result was obtained by Wulandari et al (2018), who found that managerial competence was not of general nature for any management level (one for all).

The managerial competences deemed as the most important include behaviors which are consistent with the values, ethics, and relevant regulations of law at 74.1%, followed by commitment and responsibility to finish the tasks to achieve the planned results at 72.2%, and ability to perform the public service duties professionally at 70.4%. These results can be seen in Table 3. This is the same as the managerial competences recommended by Wulandari et al (2018), i.e. customer service orientation, integrity, care for accuracy, communication and professionalism competence.

Table 3. Description of Managerial Competences

No.	Indicator	Managerial Competence Category				
		Highly Necessary	Necessary	Fairly Necessary	Unnecessary	Highly Unnecessary
1.	Behaviors which are consistent with the values, ethics, and relevant regulations of law	74.1%	25.9%	-	-	-
2.	Ability to build, nurture and maintain both internal and external cooperations	63%	37%	-	-	-
3.	Ability to communicate effectively	61.1%	38.9%	-	-	-
4.	Commitment and responsibility to finish the tasks to achieve the planned results	72.2%	27.8%	-	-	-
5.	Ability to perform public service duties professionally	70.4%	29.6%	-	-	-
6.	Ability to develop themselves and inspire others to develop	61.1%	38.9%	-	-	-
7.	Ability to keep up to date with changes, to be creative and innovative	68.5%	31.5%	-	-	-
8.	Ability to effectively make decisions	55.6%	44.4%	-	-	-

Sociocultural Competence

The sociocultural competences in this research include knowledge, skills, and attitude/behavior which can be observed, measured, and developed in relation to the experience to interact with the diverse community in terms of their religions, races and cultures, behaviors, nationalism insight, ethics, values, morals, emotions, and principles, which should be fulfilled by everyone assuming an office in order to achieve the work results which match their roles, functions, and offices. The research result indicates

that the higher the village government personnel office, the more highly they rate the sociocultural competence. The village chiefs even thought of sociocultural competence as ultimately “highly necessary” (100%). The village secretaries also thought of sociocultural competence as highly necessary (83.3%). Based on the research result, an average of 57% of village government personnel thought of sociocultural competence as “highly necessary”. The said data can be seen in Table 4.

Generally speaking, in Indonesia sociocultural competence is highly important for employees both in public and private sectors. As suggested by Sumanti (2016), Indonesia has diverse races, religions, languages, arts and localities which are deemed as the characteristic diversity of sociocultural life. Sumanti’s (2016) research objects were Civil Servants (ASN) in Aceh and North Sumatra and it was found that sociocultural competence was highly important since it dealt with the processes of building attitude, characters and behavior.

Table 4. Cross-Tabulation of Sociocultural Competence and Village Personnel Office

No.	Office	Sociocultural Competence Category				
		Highly Necessary	Necessary	Fairly Necessary	Unnecessary	Highly Unnecessary
1.	Village Chief	100%	-	-	-	-
2.	Village Secretaries	83.3%	16.7%	-	-	-
3.	Administrative Affairs Chief	50%	50%	-	-	-
4.	Financial Division Chief	66.7%	33.3%	-	-	-
5.	Planning Division Chief	50%	50%	-	-	-
6.	Governmental Section Chief	33.3%	66.7%	-	-	-
7.	Welfare Section Chief	33.3%	66.7%	-	-	-
8.	Service Section Chief	50%	50%	-	-	-
9.	Hamlet Chief	50%	50%	-	-	-
MEAN		57.4%	42.6%	-	-	-

Sumanti’s (2016) research concluded that Aceh and North Sumatra share some sociocultural competences, including: (1) the same perspective on the importance of sociocultural competence in bureaucracy since it was highly needed to interact with fellow employees and service users, in this case the community; (2) the same factors which influenced the development of sociocultural competence, i.e. religions and customs; (3) the same view of the importance of agenda to develop sociocultural competence in the institution’s work plan, and its use of this sociocultural competence as an indicator for employee placement within new environment and office.

Also found in both regions were the same values whose truths were believed in and used as a reference to behave, namely: (1) religious values as embodied in useful behavior for both their world and the after life, including respect for freedom to embrace a religion and worship; (2) ethical values such as honesty, acting in compliance with the applicable regulations, and friendly in giving services to public; (3) aesthetical values including those related to art work; and (4) social values related to interaction and relationship with others within the same environment such as hospitality, tolerance, helping each other and so forth. Mean while, in this research we conduct, the sociocultural competences found among village government personnel include (1) being capable of promoting such attitudes as tolerant, transparent, and sensitive to diversity; (2) being capable of helping the government in uniting the community amidst their diversity; and (3) being capable of maintaining, developing, and embodying unity and oneness in their lives as a community, a nation and a country.

All of these sociocultural competences found in this research are important, despite being “highly necessary” and “necessary” with no one saying them as ultimately needed. Most village government personnel thought the competence of being capable of uniting the community amidst their diversity as “highly necessary” or around 55.6%, and the competence of being able to promote such attitudes as tolerant, transparent and sensitive to diversity is deemed as “necessary” by most village personnel or 53.7%. The same goes to the competence of being capable of maintaining, developing and embodying unity and oneness where it is thought as “necessary” at 53.7%. The data can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5. Description of Sociocultural Competences

No.	Indicator	Sociocultural Competence Category				
		Highly Necessary	Necessary	Fairly Necessary	Unnecessary	Highly Unnecessary
1.	Capable of promoting such attitudes as tolerant, transparent, and sensitive to diversity	46.3%	53.7%	-	-	-
2.	Capable of helping the government in uniting the community amidst their diversity	55.6%	44.4%	-	-	-
3.	Being capable of maintaining, developing, and embodying unity and oneness in their lives as a community, a nation and a country	46.3%	53.7%	-	-	-

Technical Competence

The technical competence in this research include knowledge, skills, and attitude/behavior which can be observed, measured and developed specifically related to their office technical fields. This is almost identical to the concept suggested by Maarif et al (2017) in their research on the quality of supervision by Government Internal Supervisory Personnel or *Aparat Pengawas Internal Pemerintah* (APIP) in Aceh, in which technical competence is defined as the specific abilities the auditor officer or APIP should own in performing their duties.

This research result shows that village government personnel think of technical competence as “necessary” in performing their office duties. An average of 81.5% view technical competence as “necessary”. From the research result, it can also be seen there is the tendency that the lower the office position, the more likely for village personnel to think of technical competence as more “necessary” and some even think of it as ultimately “necessary” at 100% such as the offices of Administrative Affairs Chief, Planning Affairs Chief, Governmental Section Chief and Service Section Chief. These data can be seen in Table 6.

Another study result also showed that technical competence was highly important since it would determine the quality of result of audit performed by APIP. Knowledge and expertise which were the indicators of technical competence could support the auditor thought in solving problems and making decisions from the audit object. Therefore, it was important for APIP to have technical competence in performing their duties (Maarif et al., 2017; Sulaiman, 2005; Subhan, 2012; Covey et al, 1994).

Table 6. Cross-Tabulation of Technical Competence and Village Personnel Office

No.	Office	Technical Competence Category				
		Highly Necessary	Necessary	Fairly Necessary	Unnecessary	Highly Unnecessary
1.	Village Chief	83,3%	16,7%	-	-	-
2.	Village Secretaries	33,3%	66,7%	-	-	-
3.	Administrative Affairs Chief	-	100%	-	-	-
4.	Financial Division Chief	16,7%	83,3%	-	-	-
5.	Planning Division Chief	-	100%	-	-	-
6.	Governmental Section Chief	-	100%	-	-	-
7.	Welfare Section Chief	16,7%	83,3%	-	-	-
8.	Service Section Chief	-	100%	-	-	-
9.	Hamlet Chief	16,7%	83,3%	-	-	-
MEAN		18,5%	81,5%	-	-	-

In this research, the technical competence is sorted into two, namely generic and specific technical competences. The generic technical competence is the one every office holder dealing with village governmental affairs must own. The specific technical competence is the one owned only those certain offices dealing with village governmental affairs as their office duties.

Generic Technical Competence

The research result indicates that most village personnel (74.1%) think of generic technical competence as “necessary”. This is of course consistent with the definition of generic technical competence that all existing offices should own generic competence, with some even stating that it is ultimately necessary (100%), i.e. the Administrative Affairs Chief and Governmental Section Chief. These data can be seen in Table 7.

Table 7. Cross-Tabulation of Generic Technical Competence and Village Personnel Office

No.	Office	Generic Technical Competence Category				
		Highly Necessary	Necessary	Fairly Necessary	Unnecessary	Highly Unnecessary
1.	Village Chief	83.3%	16.7%	-	-	-
2.	Village Secretaries	33.3%	66.7%	-	-	-
3.	Administrative Affairs Chief	-	100%	-	-	-
4.	Financial Division Chief	33.3%	66.7%	-	-	-
5.	Planning Division Chief	16.7%	83.3%	-	-	-
6.	Governmental Section Chief	-	100%	-	-	-
7.	Welfare Section Chief	16.7%	83.3%	-	-	-
8.	Service Section Chief	16.7%	83.3%	-	-	-
9.	Hamlet Chief	33.3%	66.7%	-	-	-
MEAN		25.9%	74.1%	-	-	-

Based on the research result, the found generic technical competences include: (1) ability to administer the village government; (2) capable of performing village development; (3) capable of nurturing the community; and (4) capable of empowering the community. The research result indicates that most village government personnel agree that every type of generic technical competence is “necessary” at over 75% and the one rated as the most necessary is the competence of empowering the community. The data can be seen in Table 8.

Table 8. Description of Generic Technical Competence

No.	Indicator	Generic Technical Competence Category				
		Highly Necessary	Necessary	Fairly Necessary	Unnecessary	Highly Unnecessary
1.	Ability to administer the village government	24.1%	75.9%	-	-	-
2.	Ability of performing village development	16.7%	83.3%	-	-	-
3.	Ability to nurture the community	24.1%	75.9%	-	-	-
4.	Ability to empower the community	14.8%	85.2%	-	-	-

Specific Technical Competence

The research result indicates that most village government personnel agree that specific technical competence is “necessary” at a mean of 83.3% and some even state it is absolutely necessary (100%), i.e. Administrative Affairs Chief, Planning Affairs Chief, Governmental Section Chief, and Service Section Chief. The data can be seen in Table 9.

Table 9. Cross-Tabulation of Specific Technical Competence and Village Personnel Office

No.	Office	Specific Technical Competence Category				
		Highly Necessary	Necessary	Fairly Necessary	Unnecessary	Highly Unnecessary
1.	Village Chief	83.3%	16.7%	-	-	-
2.	Village Secretaries	16.7%	83.3%	-	-	-
3.	Administrative Affairs Chief	-	100%	-	-	-
4.	Financial Division Chief	16.7%	83.3%	-	-	-
5.	Planning Division Chief	-	100%	-	-	-
6.	Governmental Section Chief	-	100%	-	-	-
7.	Welfare Section Chief	16.7%	83.3%	-	-	-
8.	Service Section Chief	-	100%	-	-	-
9.	Hamlet Chief	16.7%	83.3%	-	-	-
MEAN		16.7%	83.3%	-	-	-

Based on the research results, the specific technical competences deemed as necessary include: (1) establishing village regulations; (2) organizing counseling on land affairs; (3) performing counseling on public order; (4) performing protection for the public; (5) organizing demographic administration; (6) performing spatial planning and zoning; (7) performing physical construction; (8) improving public participation; (9) performing non-physical development; (10) performing counseling on citizenship rights and duties; (11) building partnership with civil or other institutions; (12) organizing administrative affairs; (13) administering general affairs (facilities, infrastructures, and human resource department); (14) administering financial affairs; and (15) administering planning affairs. Each specific technical competence by village government personnel is deemed as “necessary” at 75% respectively. The data can be seen in Table 10.

Table 10. Description of Specific Technical Competence

No.	Indicator	Specific Technical Competence Category				
		Highly Necessary	Necessary	Fairly Necessary	Unnecessary	Highly Unnecessary
1.	Ability to establish village regulations	18.5%	79.6%	1.9%	-	-
2.	Ability to organize counseling on land affairs	20.4%	79.6%	-	-	-
3.	Ability to perform counseling on public order	16.7%	83.3%	-	-	-
4.	Ability to perform community protection effort	16.7%	83.3%	-	-	-
5.	Ability to organize demographic administration	14.8%	85.2%	-	-	-
6.	Ability to perform spatial planning and zoning	13.0%	87.0%	-	-	-
7.	Ability to perform physical construction	13.0%	77.8%	9.3%	-	-
8.	Ability to improve public participation	16.7%	83.3%	-	-	-
9.	Ability to perform non-physical development	24.1%	75.9%	-	-	-

10.	Ability to organize counseling on citizenship rights and responsibility	14.8%	85.2%	-	-	-
11.	Ability to build partnership with civil and other institutions	14.8%	85.2%	-	-	-
12.	Ability to organize administrative affairs	16.7%	83.3%	-	-	-
13.	Ability to administer general affairs (facilities, infrastructures, and human resource department)	14.8%	85.2%	-	-	-
14.	Ability to organize financial affairs	16.7%	83.3%	-	-	-
15.	Ability to administer planning affairs	16.7%	83.3%	-	-	-

E. CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion above, it can be concluded that generally village government personnel in Banyumas Regency think of office competences as something necessary to facilitate them in performing their office duties. The competences they deem necessary include: (1) managerial competence; (2) sociocultural competence; (3) technical competence, both generic and specific ones.

Both managerial, sociocultural, and (generic and specific) technical competences have all been identified and all of these competences are deemed either “highly necessary” or “necessary”. Therefore, these findings ought to be used as the basis for preparing competence dictionary and competence standards for village government personnel offices.

The recommendation the writer can offer is that in order for the competence-based development of village government personnel to be immediately organized, there is a need to test the village government personnel competences and map them. From there on wards, an effective model can be prepared to develop village government personnel based on competences.

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